

Validation of Magneto-Inertial Measurement Units for Upper-Limb Motion Analysis through an Anthropomorphic Robot

Martina Lapresa^{1†*}, Christian Tamantini^{1†}, Francesco Scotto di Luzio¹, Marco Ferlazzo², Gianfranco Sorrenti², Flavio Corpina² and Loredana Zollo¹

I. INTRODUCTION

Kinematic analysis of human movement is paramount in many fields to objectively quantify joint angular displacements and Range of Motion (RoM) of human limbs. These include, but not limited to, physical rehabilitation [1, 2] and ergonomic evaluation of working gestures [3] and postures in occupational contexts [4].

To date, many tools have been proposed to perform human kinematic analysis and RoM assessment. Optoelectronic motion capture systems are nowadays considered the gold standard for movement analysis [1], especially for gait analysis. Thanks to their accuracy, motion capture systems can be adopted as ground truth for the validation of novel measurement tools, measuring joint angles during dynamic movements with multiple Degrees of Freedom (DoFs) [5]. However, optoelectronic motion capture systems are expensive, not portable and can be affected by markers' occlusion events. For these reasons, their use is limited to very structured settings and expert people are required to perform the analysis [1, 5].

In this scenario, Magneto-Inertial Measurement Units (M-IMUs) have been already adopted in the state-of-the-art to quantify joint angular displacements in both clinical (e.g. objective assessment and rehabilitation) [6, 7, 8] and ergonomic [9, 10, 11, 12] applications. Nine-axis M-IMUs combine a 3-axis accelerometer, a 3-axis gyroscope and a 3-axis magnetometer. The information captured by accelerometers, gyroscopes and magnetometers is combined to estimate the sensor orientation with respect to a global reference frame. Data fusion algorithms, such as Kalman or Complementary filters, provide a reliable estimation of M-IMU orientation (and, therefore, of the body segment where the sensor is positioned) [1]. Moreover, M-IMUs have the advantage of being small, wearable, portable and wireless in many cases. They can be fixed to the body segments to objectively compute joint angles, overcoming the drawbacks of the optoelectronic motion capture systems. For instance, the ergonomic evalua-

tion of workers can benefit from the unobtrusiveness of such devices, thus enabling to monitor the movements performed during working activities with minimum impediment.

Moreover, in order to provide an accurate estimation of body segments orientation, the local axes of the sensors must be aligned to the anatomical counterparts, and a preliminary calibration step is typically required before performing the kinematic analysis [4, 5].

To establish the suitability of novel M-IMUs for joint angle measurement in clinical applications as well as ergonomic evaluation of workers, it is essential to assess their performance in terms of accuracy, i.e. the closeness of the measurement to the true value.

Recent works have widely investigated the state-of-the-art devices and their performance in joint angle estimation. The review by Poitras et al. [1] focuses on the use of M-IMUs for the whole body kinematic analysis. The systematic review by Walmsley et al. [5] is mainly focused on M-IMUs used to monitor upper limb joint angles. Both reviews collect works about the validation of M-IMUs and report results about the accuracy of such systems. The literature points out that the characterization of the accuracy of M-IMU sensors can be carried out by comparing the angle measured by the sensor with the angle estimated by a gold standard system, such as an optoelectronic motion capture system or a robotic device.

If an optoelectronic motion capture system is used the M-IMUs as well as the retro-reflective markers should be positioned on specific anatomical landmarks. In this type of validation, the volunteers are asked to perform specific movements tracked synchronously by the two systems [13, 14, 15, 16]. The joint angles reconstructed by the optoelectronic motion capture system are compared with the sensor output. However, specific kinematic protocols must be applied to retrieve joint angles and allow comparisons. This introduces additional complexity that may affect the validation procedure [17]. Moreover, interpolation could be required in presence of marker occlusions, thus introducing sources of approximation in the identification of marker trajectories [18].

The validation approach grounded on robotic devices exploits the high accuracy and repeatability of robots while executing movements and their capability to directly measure angles, overcoming the sources of errors introduced by optoelectronic motion capture systems. Robotic systems are able to truly estimate the measurement error of the sensor [5]. In literature, some works that validate M-IMUs through upper limb

[†] These authors equally contributed to the work;

¹ Unit of Advanced Robotics and Human-Centred Technologies, Università Campus Bio-Medico di Roma, Rome, 00128, Italy;

² Istituto Clinico Polispecialistico Cure Ortopediche Traumatologiche s.p.a., Messina, 98124, Italy;

This work was supported partly by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme with ODIN project (CUP: C85F21000670006) and SOMA project (CUP: C82F20000090006) and partly by Regione Lazio with HeAL9000 project (CUP: B84I20001880002).

movements, reproduced by a robotic device, can be found. The performance of M-IMUs is quantified by means of a robot executing planar and complex movements in [19], and constant speed rotations and linear translations in [17]. Movements are executed at different speeds in both works. In [20], Ricci et al. quantifies the orientation tracking performance of two filters by means of a robot executing movements at different frequencies and amplitudes. In the work [21], the authors simulate flexion/extension movements of the elbow with a robot. In [4] and [22], two degrees-of-freedom mechanical devices produce static poses and are used to validate M-IMUs in laboratory settings. However, the movements reproduced in these works do not take into account the typical speeds or RoMs of the human motion. Thus, the obtained results cannot be directly used to characterize the M-IMU behaviour for human upper-limb motion analysis. Moreover, particular attention should be paid to the effect of the magnetic field produced by the electric motors on the sensors, especially if they include a magnetometer. Only Alvarez et al. [4] repeats the tests in different laboratory settings to take into account the effect of possible magnetic field perturbations, and points out that magnetic or ferromagnetic material close to the sensor causes distortions in the measured magnetic field.

Therefore, a preliminary analysis of magnetic disturbances should be carried out before running the experiments [4].

Given the evidence in the literature, it is worth investigating a new method for assessing accuracy of M-IMUs for human motion analysis that can overcome limitations of previous studies in the literature, described above. Hence, this work wants to propose a new method, grounded on the use of an anthropomorphic robot, to characterize the behaviour of M-IMUs in frequency and amplitude ranges typical of human movement. The use of a robot allows generating controlled and repeatable angular trajectories, thus providing a gold standard to evaluate the capability of the sensors to accurately track target angular trajectories. With respect to the current validation procedures, the method proposed in this work tries to incorporate key-elements for characterizing M-IMUs performance in human motion analysis. In detail: i) it includes a magnetic disturbance assessment, ii) it analyzes the dynamic behaviour of the sensors at different human frequencies and iii) it characterizes the sensors by simulating human upper limb movements with the robot, taking into account the physiological ranges of motion and movement speeds. We want to reproduce typical conditions of human motion, by replicating with the robot speeds and RoMs typical of human movement. Otherwise, the validation fails to provide a functional assessment. In the proposed method, the Root Mean Square Error (*RMSE*) [5], estimated as the error between the sensors measurements and the angular values provided by the robot encoders, is adopted as performance indicator. The proposed workflow can be exploited to characterize the sensor behaviour for different applications as well as the sensor fusion algorithms implemented into the measurement unit. This work is organized as follows: in Section II, the proposed workflow, tests and the experimental validation are described. Section III presents the obtained results and discussions. Conclusions and future work are reported in Section IV.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this section, the proposed approach for the characterization of M-IMUs with a robotic system is described. The block scheme that summarizes the proposed approach is reported in Fig. 1. In brief, the proposed validation protocol is composed of three main steps: i) Magnetic Disturbance Assessment, to quantify the magnetic field acting on the M-IMUs and, consequently, identify the optimal robot configuration to perform the experiments and the sensors positioning; ii) Human Movement Assessment, including frequency and amplitude validations, to estimate the behavior of the M-IMUs in tracking human movements; iii) Post-processing and RMSE Computation. The proposed validation protocol wants to characterize the performance of the sensor in the application range in which the sensor is intended to be used by means of a set of experimental acquisitions.

The frequency range of interest for human movement analysis is chosen by analyzing the power spectrum of the human motions. In fact, most activities of daily living performed by healthy subjects are characterized by an average predominant frequency component at 1 Hz and the 75% of the spectral energy is condensed under 5 Hz [23]. The amplitude range of interest can be selected according to the movement and anatomical district that is intended to be monitored. Once selected the range of amplitudes to be tested, the speed of the movements executed by the robot should be similar to human ones. Then, the trajectory the robot has to perform must be planned and orientation data should be collected synchronously from the M-IMUs and the robot encoders, and saved for post-processing analysis.

Fig. 1. Block scheme of the proposed validation protocol.

A. Proposed Validation Protocol

1) *Magnetic disturbance assessment*: As previously introduced in Section I, the use of a robotic device to validate M-IMUs entails the necessity of quantifying possible magnetic disturbances generated by the robot actuation system, and identifying the optimal robot configuration and sensor positioning, in order to set the robot and the sensors in an optimal configuration. In fact, the magnetic field, measured by the M-IMU, is used to compute the orientation with respect to the Global fixed Reference Frame *GRF* of the sensor. The robot motors and magnetic brakes can produce some distortions of the Earth magnetic field, therefore a preliminary evaluation of the magnetic field disturbance must be carried out by positioning one sensor directly close to the robot electric

motors. The raw magnetic field data $\mathbf{m} = [m_x, m_y, m_z]$, measured by the magnetometers mounted inside the sensor, should be collected both with the robot turned ON and OFF. Hence, the Mean (M) and Standard Deviation (MSD) of the magnetic field norm are evaluated to quantify the magnetic field.

The aforementioned indicators (M and MSD) should be computed for both conditions (with the robot turned ON and OFF) and compared to evaluate the presence of magnetic field disturbance. If results show a significant disturbance induced by the robot motors, sensors should be positioned as far as possible from the motors, for example on a custom made flange attached to the robot end-effector [24].

2) *Human Movement Assessment*: Once the magnetic field disturbance is assessed and the best sensors positioning on the robot is chosen, the robot can be controlled to execute repeatable and accurate movements.

The experimental acquisitions of the M-IMUs are composed of two different phases to characterize the sensors behaviour in the human frequency and amplitude ranges:

- 1) **Frequency validation phase**: it aims at evaluating the accuracy of the sensors in tracking a sinusoidal rotation produced by the joints of the robot at different frequencies;
- 2) **Amplitude validation phase**: it aims at replicating with the robot the motion of the upper limb in a given set of amplitude ranges at different speeds, to assess the sensor accuracy in tracking the reproduced movements.

In this way, it is possible to evaluate the sensor performances in tracking movements with frequency and amplitudes ranges of interest. At the beginning of each experimental trial, a 3-seconds static calibration of the M-IMUs is necessary.

3) *Post-processing and RMSE computation*: The orientation measured in the initial calibration phase by the sensor S at the time step t_0 , can be expressed with the rotation matrix $R_S^{GRF}(t_0)$, where GRF is the global reference frame of the sensor. If $R_S^{GRF}(t_i)$ is the rotation matrix that expresses the orientation of the sensor with respect to GRF at the generic time step t_i of the trial, the relative rotation of the sensor with respect to its initial orientation, at a generic time step t_i , can be described with the rotation matrix

$$R_S(t_i) = (R_S^{GRF}(t_0))^{-1} \cdot R_S^{GRF}(t_i) = \begin{bmatrix} r_{11} & r_{12} & r_{13} \\ r_{21} & r_{22} & r_{23} \\ r_{31} & r_{32} & r_{33} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where r_{mn} is the $[m, n]$ element of the rotation matrix $R_S(t_i)$. For each sensor, the Euler angles ($\theta_x^S, \theta_y^S, \theta_z^S$) can be extracted from the rotation matrix through the computation of the inverse problem of Euler angles, following the XYZ decomposition, as follows

$$\begin{cases} \theta_x^S = \text{Atan2}(r_{32}, r_{33}) \\ \theta_y^S = \text{Atan2}(-r_{31}, \sqrt{r_{32}^2 + r_{33}^2}) \\ \theta_z^S = \text{Atan2}(r_{21}, r_{11}) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

assuming that $\theta_y^S \in (-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2})$.

To evaluate the accuracy of the M-IMUs in tracking the target trajectory profile, the Root Mean Square Error ($RMSE$) [5] can be computed as

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\theta^R(t_i) - \theta_k^S(t_i))^2}, \quad (3)$$

where θ^R and θ^S are the angular values measured by the robot encoders and by the M-IMU, respectively, N is the number of samples in the trial and $k = \{x, y, z\}$.

B. Experimental Validation

To demonstrate the applicability of the proposed approach, it was applied to two different sets of M-IMUs. The robot used to validate the sensors is the the KUKA LWR 4+ (KUKA GmbH, Germany), shown in Fig. 2a. The KUKA robot has 7 DoFs arranged in an anthropomorphic chain, highlighted in Fig. 2b. Each DoF is equipped with a motor and a 16-bit magnetic encoder capable of measuring current joint angle with an accuracy higher than $2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ rad.

Fig. 2. The KUKA LWR 4+ robotic arm used in this study. In (a) the robot joints, the fixed reference frame $O_b - \vec{x}_b \vec{y}_b \vec{z}_b$ and the \vec{z}_{ee} axis are highlighted. In (b) the kinematic chain of the robot is shown.

A very finely controlled motion, at a frame rate of 1 kHz, can be generated with this robotic device. The pose of the robot end-effector can be computed by means of a forward kinematics with respect to the robot global reference frame $O_b - \vec{x}_b \vec{y}_b \vec{z}_b$, placed at the robot base. In this work, the robot is controlled by using a joint position control. The trajectory planner and controller are developed under the Robot Operating System (ROS) framework onto a Linux-based development computer.

The two sets of M-IMUs are the WISE sensors (WISE, NCS Lab S.R.L., Carpi, Italy), shown in Fig. 3a, and the XSens MTw (XSens, The Netherlands), shown in Fig. 3b. Both the global $x_G y_G z_G$ and local reference frames $x_w y_w z_w$ and $x_x y_x z_x$ of the WISE and XSens sensors, respectively, are highlighted in Fig. 3c. Each WISE sensor incorporates 3-axis accelerometers, gyroscopes and magnetometers, and an integrated processor that manages the sampling, buffering, calibration and sensor-fusion algorithms of inertial and magnetic data, as well as the wireless network protocol for data transmission. The electronics of the sensors is embedded inside a light and small plastic case. Each sensor weights 27 g and has $44.30 \times 33.80 \times 15.20$ mm dimensions. Each WISE sensor provides both the raw data (accelerometer, magnetometer, gyroscope) and the computed sensor orientation exploiting a Kalman filter technique.

The WISE sensors are part of Showmotion (NCS Lab S.R.L., Carpi, Italy), a system for real-time biomechanical analysis of the human body.

On the other hand, the weight of each XSens M-IMU is 16 g with a dimension of $47 \times 30 \times 13$ mm. The raw measurements of the 3-axis accelerometers, gyroscopes and magnetometers are integrated by means of a complementary filter [25].

The orientation of the local reference frame of the sensors is expressed with respect to a *GRF*. More specifically, the *GRF* is defined using the North-West-Up (NWU) convention, in which the x_G , y_G and z_G axes point to magnetic North, magnetic West and upward respectively (see Fig. 3c).

Fig. 3. (a) WISE sensors connected to the recharge case and dedicated receiver, (b) XSens MTw sensor and the USB receiver, (c) global and local reference frame xy_z of the WISE and XSens sensors.

The robot joint angular positions and the end-effector rotations are saved and synchronized with the data collected by the WISE and XSens sensors at 70 Hz.

1) *Magnetic disturbance assessment*: The first phase of the proposed validation protocol involves the magnetic disturbance assessment. Sensors are placed near the robot motors and the raw magnetic field is recorded for both sensors (WISE and XSens) with the robot turned ON and OFF.

Given the significant disturbance induced by the robot electric motors on the sensors positioned directly at the robot end-effector, quantified in Section III, a flange to house the sensors and keep them far from the sources of magnetic disturbance is developed. The flange is designed and 3D-printed in polylactic acid (PLA) to house up to seven sensors in different configurations. It can be fixed to the end-effector of the robot. The main design requirements are i) to have a limited weight, in order to comply with the payload of the robotic arm (14 kg), ii) to reduce interference effects between sensors through appropriate positioning in the housing and iii) to be far enough from the last motor, which can induce a magnetic field, thus altering the measurement. The resulting load of the flange is 0.9 kg and the guaranteed distance between one sensor and the other is 0.08 m. The height of the overall flange is 0.2 m. The flange allows positioning the sensors in different configurations in order to align the \vec{x} , \vec{y} and \vec{z} axis of the sensors with the axis \vec{z}_{ee} . The developed flange is shown in Fig. 4c.

The M and MSD indicators are computed for the two tested sensor systems. The acquisition lasts 30 seconds and is carried out for three configurations of the robot (0 , $\frac{\pi}{4}$ and $\frac{\pi}{2}$) in which the robot kinematic chain is fixed to align the rotation axes of joints 5 and 7 (\vec{z}_{ee}) with one of the

three versors $\{\vec{v}_0; \vec{v}_{\frac{\pi}{4}}; \vec{v}_{\frac{\pi}{2}}\}$. In particular, $\vec{v}_0 = [0, 0, 1]^T$, $\vec{v}_{\frac{\pi}{4}} = [\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}, 0, \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}]^T$ and $\vec{v}_{\frac{\pi}{2}} = [1, 0, 0]^T$ expressed in the robot fixed reference frame $O_b - \vec{x}_b \vec{y}_b \vec{z}_b$, are described in Fig. 4a. In this way, \vec{z}_{ee} is aligned with the gravitational axis for the configuration 0. Otherwise, it forms a $\frac{\pi}{4}$ rad and a $\frac{\pi}{2}$ rad angle with the vertical direction in the configuration $\frac{\pi}{4}$ and $\frac{\pi}{2}$, respectively. Fig. 4b shows the robot kinematic chain fixed in the three aforementioned configurations. These three robot configurations have been tested to identify the best configuration for performing the first phase of the protocol and minimize the magnetic disturbance on the sensors measurements. The best configuration is the $\pi/2$ one, as discussed in Section III.

2) *Experimental Validation 1 – Frequency Validation Phase*: In the first validation phase, joints 5 and 7 of the robot (see Fig. 2a) are controlled to execute rotations to track a sinusoidal trajectory profile. Eq. (4) reports the sinusoidal waveform implemented.

$$\theta_j(t) = Amp \cdot \sin(2\pi f \cdot t) \quad (4)$$

where $j = \{5, 7\}$ is the actuated joint, Amp and f are the amplitude and frequency of the desired oscillation, θ_j is the joint angle around the \vec{z}_{ee} axis and t is the current time.

The tested frequency set is $f = \{0.18, 0.32, 0.56, 1, 1.78, 3.16\}$ Hz. The selected frequency set allows characterizing the sensors behaviour in the human operating range. In order to collect a dataset of sinusoidal motions, a set of amplitudes is defined. The Amp have been selected in order to deal with safety constraints on the maximum torque sustainable at the KUKA LWR 4+ robot joints. The chosen amplitude set for the sinusoidal trajectory profile is $Amp = \{0.05, 0.08, 0.1, 0.15, 0.17, 0.31\}$ rad. In particular, the amplitudes $Amp = \{0.05, 0.08, 0.15\}$ rad are generated by controlling joint 7 of the robotic arm ($\theta_5 = 0$ rad); the other ones are performed by the synchronous actuation of joints 5 and 7, i. e. the two joints having their rotational axis parallel with \vec{z}_{ee} , to obtain a total rotation of amplitude $Amp = \{0.1, 0.17, 0.31\}$ rad. The chosen amplitude and frequency values are combined to generate different sinusoidal profiles. Each resulting movement is performed for 20 s.

These trials are performed in the best robot configuration that allows the minimization of the magnetic field disturbance (see Section III). Each trial is recorded with three WISE and three XSens, positioned as in Fig. 4c.

At the beginning of each experimental trial, a 3-seconds static calibration of the M-IMUs is performed. The $RMSE$ is computed as in Eq. (3) for each frequency and amplitude pair.

3) *Experimental Validation 2 – Amplitude Validation Phase*: The DoFs of the upper limb can be reproduced by the anthropomorphic KUKA LWR 4+ robot. In this case, the following movements of the human upper limb are reproduced using the robot: shoulder flexion/extension (sFE), shoulder adduction/abduction (sAA), shoulder intra/extra-rotation (sIE), elbow flexion/extension (eFE), wrist pronosupination (wPS), wrist flexion/extension (wFE) and wrist radio/ulnar deviation (wRUD). Fig. 5 shows the correspondence between the robot

Fig. 4. In (a) the \vec{z}_{ee} axis is aligned with $\{\vec{v}_0; \vec{v}_{\pi/4}; \vec{v}_{\pi/2}\}$, expressed with respect to the fixed reference frame of the robot. In (b) the experimental setup for the three tested configurations is shown. The flange developed to house up to seven sensors (c).

joints (Fig. 5a) and the anatomical DoFs of the human upper limb (Fig. 5b).

Fig. 5. Correspondence between the robot joints and the anatomical DoFs of the human upper limb. In (a) the reference frame of each robot joint is reported, the rotation axis \vec{z} of each joint is colored in blue, and in (b) the human upper limb DoFs are highlighted. The table in (c) reports the actuated robot joints and physiological RoMs.

The physiological RoMs of the human upper limb joints are considered to resemble human-like motions. Table in Fig 5c resumes the reproduced DoF, the corresponding actuated robot joint, indicated with their angular value, and the physiological RoM [26]. In particular, flexion, adduction, intra-rotation, pronation and wrist ulnar deviation are expressed with positive angular values; on the other hand extension, abduction, extra-rotation, supination and wrist radial deviation are expressed with negative angular values.

In this experimental phase the joint trajectory is planned by using a fifth order polynomial in order to ensure continuous velocities and accelerations and avoid irregular curvature.

Theoretically, to reconstruct the kinematics of the upper limb, three M-IMUs should be positioned on the robot to track the movement the arm, the forearm and the wrist. Moreover, an additional M-IMU is required to define the thorax fixed reference frame. Thorax, arm, forearm and wrist will be indexed as $\{T, A, F, W\}$, respectively. The sensors should be positioned as shown in Fig. 5a. The thorax sensor T should have its local \vec{x} , \vec{y} and \vec{z} -axis parallel with the $-\vec{x}$, \vec{z} and \vec{y} axis of the robot base reference frame respectively. The sensors A and F should be aligned with the links of the robot to have their \vec{x} local axis parallel with the greatest dimension of the link. The sensor at the wrist W should be positioned with its local \vec{z} axis parallel to $-\vec{z}_{ee}$ and its local \vec{x} axis parallel to the \vec{x} local axis of the F sensor.

Unfortunately, the magnetic disturbance induced by the robot on the sensors directly positioned on the robot could falsify the orientation estimated by the sensors. Therefore, the upper limb movements are tracked by exploiting only two sensors, one used as a fixed reference and positioned far from the robot base to avoid magnetic disturbance, and one positioned on the flange used for the first validation phase to ensure the minimization of the magnetic disturbance. In particular, the fixed reference sensors are $\{T, A, F\}$, according to the specific DoF, oriented as shown in Fig. 5a. For each reproduced DoF, the fixed sensor will act as the fixed anatomical district, whereas the sensor on the flange will act as the one tracking the moving anatomical district. The sensor tracking the moving anatomical district, i.e. A, F and W , is positioned on the flange to respect the theoretical alignment with the robot links. This solution is suitable for this particular application because the computation of the relative rotation between two sensors is invariant to sensors rigid translations. Moreover, for each considered DoF, the physiological RoM and speed is respected.

The experimental protocol of this validation phase consists in making the robot execute angular excursions of each joint from negative to positive values of the physiological RoM interval, and vice-versa (see Table in Fig 5c). Two consecutive repetitions for each of the seven considered DoFs are recorded. For every DoF, eight trials are repeated. Each trial is repeated with two different rotational speed values. In particular, the average speed values during the movement are set as 0.17 rad/s and 0.34 rad/s for all the considered DoF since they are typical of the human movement. Then, the time to complete the movements is computed in order to respect the constraints imposed on the speed. In this way, it is possible to evaluate the performance of the sensors in tracking anthropomorphic movements executed at different speeds.

The relative rotations between the fixed and the moving sensor are then computed. Referring to $R_T^{GRF}(t_i)$, $R_A^{GRF}(t_i)$, $R_F^{GRF}(t_i)$ and $R_W^{GRF}(t_i)$ as the rotation matrices of the reference frames of the M-IMUs with respect to the global reference frame GRF , at a generic time step t_i , for $i = 1, \dots, N$, where N is the number of collected samples, it is possible to compute the relative rotation between two consecutive sensors. The relative rotation between the arm and the trunk allows the computation of the shoulder angles; similarly, the relative rotation between the forearm and the arm allows computing the elbow angle, whereas the relative rotation between the

wrist and the forearm allows measuring the wrist angular excursions. In particular, these rotation matrices are expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} R_A^T(t_i) &= (R_T^{GRF}(t_i))^{-1} \cdot R_A^{GRF}(t_i) \\ R_F^A(t_i) &= (R_A^{GRF}(t_i))^{-1} \cdot R_F^{GRF}(t_i) \\ R_W^F(t_i) &= (R_F^{GRF}(t_i))^{-1} \cdot R_W^{GRF}(t_i). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The inverse problem of the Euler angles is computed as in Eq. (2) from the rotation matrices following the XYZ decomposition with respect to current frames, to retrieve $\Phi = [\varphi, \theta, \psi]^T$.

The monitored Euler angles for each DoF are: θ_A^T for the sFE , ψ_A^T for the sAA , φ_A^T for the sIE , ψ_F^A for the eFE , θ_W^F for the wFE , φ_W^F for the wPS , ψ_W^F for the $wRUD$. For the sake of brevity, the array $\mathbf{Eul} = [\theta_A^T, \psi_A^T, \varphi_A^T, \psi_F^A, \theta_W^F, \varphi_W^F, \psi_W^F]^T$ is introduced in order to refer to the considered Euler angle extracted from the sensors for each DoF. $RMSE$ performance indicator, computed as in Eq. (3), is used to assess the accuracy in tracking the anthropomorphic movements.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The influence of the magnetic field produced by the robot motors and magnetic brakes on the sensor measurements is evaluated through the computation of the M and MSD of the norm of the magnetic field measured by the sensors positioned on the robot, with the robot both turned ON and OFF. The $M \pm MSD$ of the norm of the magnetic field measured by the WISE and XSens sensors positioned on the robot is 0.3584 ± 0.0176 G for the robot turned OFF and 0.6561 ± 0.0212 G for the robot turned ON, and 0.3385 ± 0.0171 G for the robot turned OFF and 0.6259 ± 0.0195 G for the robot turned ON for the WISE and XSens sensor respectively. The $M \pm MSD$ of the norm of the magnetic field measured by each sensor positioned on the custom-made flange, for each configuration of the robot $0, \frac{\pi}{4}$ and $\frac{\pi}{2}$ are reported in Table I. The values of the magnetic field measured by the sensors when placed on the flange are in the range of the Earth magnetic field ($0.25 - 0.65$ G [27]), whereas a significant disturbance induced by the robot motors is quantifiable when the sensors are placed directly on the robot. The magnetic disturbance, in fact, can affect the sensor measurement as reported in [4].

Fig. 6 shows a representative trial for the frequency and amplitude validation phases of the protocol, in which the behaviour of the sensors in tracking the target trajectory is appreciable. In particular, Figs. 6a and 6b represent the sinusoidal trajectory, and Figs. 6c and 6d illustrate the sAA movement reproduced by the robot and tracked by the WISE and XSens sensors, respectively. As evident in Figs. 6a and 6b, it is worth observing that the sensors did not exhibit drift in the static condition.

Fig. 7 shows the $RMSE$ computed in the frequency validation phase, averaged on the three WISE and XSens sensors. Errors are computed for the given frequency set at different amplitudes. A linear regression is performed for each frequency to estimate the $RMSE$ trend outside the tested conditions. Once an acceptable error threshold is selected by the user for the intended application, the set of frequencies

Fig. 6. Representative sinusoidal and anthropomorphic trajectories collected during the experimental acquisition are reported in (a-b) and (c-d), respectively.

that satisfies the error requirements can be retrieved. In the example reported in Fig. 7 a threshold of 0.087 rad is chosen because, according to the literature evidences [1], such an error is considered to be acceptable for the intended application. However, this is just an example and does not affect the validity of the approach. Given the selected threshold, the percentage of occurrences in which the error is below 0.087 rad is 87.96% and 71.30% for WISE and XSens sensors, respectively (computed on the 108 calculated $RMSE$). Moreover, the error increases with the frequency of the movements, with a similar slope for all the tested frequencies for the WISE sensors. The increasing trend of the errors with the frequency is in line with the results presented in [20], where the authors report that the median orientation errors significantly raise with the increasing movement frequencies of the robot. For the XSens, the behavior is similar, except for the two highest frequencies, and is in line with the results provided in [20], where the absolute error ranges in $[0.01, 0.14]$ rad.

Fig. 8 illustrates the errors computed in the amplitude validation phase for the two classes of sensors at two different velocities S_1 and S_2 . The boxplot resumes the median value computed on the 8 performed trials and the interquartile ranges. The results obtained for the two tested motion speeds are colored in blue and red for S_1 and S_2 , respectively. Similarly to the frequency validation phase, the final user can set an acceptable error threshold, thus defining the movements that can be monitored with the required accuracy. The highest errors (≥ 0.087 rad) are related to the sIE and wPS movements, that are executed as a rotation around the same axis (see Fig. 5a). These obtained errors match those obtained in previous works. It was already demonstrated in [18] that the DoF exhibiting the highest tracking errors is the sIE . For all the other movements, errors are below the selected threshold. The errors obtained for wrist motions fall in $[0.03, 0.17]$ rad in [4]. $RMSE$ ranging in $[0.003, 0.21]$ rad are reported in [17] in which the sensors are validated with trapezoidal angular tra-

TABLE I
MAGNETIC FIELD DISTURBANCE FOR THE FIRST VALIDATION PHASE: MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION OF THE NORM OF THE MAGNETIC FIELD ARE REPORTED FOR THE TWO TESTED SENSORS.

	0		$\pi/4$		$\pi/2$	
[G]	Robot ON	Robot OFF	Robot ON	Robot OFF	Robot ON	Robot OFF
WISE	0.3485 ± 0.0004	0.3420 ± 0.0004	0.3392 ± 0.0016	0.3381 ± 0.0005	0.3535 ± 0.0018	0.3522 ± 0.0004
XSens	0.3419 ± 0.0022	0.3268 ± 0.0017	0.3289 ± 0.0017	0.3249 ± 0.0021	0.3822 ± 0.0009	0.3819 ± 0.0011

Fig. 7. *RMSE* of the trials acquired during the frequency validation phase for the two sensor systems.

jectories executed at speeds much higher than the ones typical of human movements. Therefore, the error ranges obtained in this paper for the tested sensors, $[0.029, 0.120]$ rad and $[0.061, 0.259]$ rad for WISE and Xsens respectively, are in line with those of the literature. Although the results presented in this paper match the literature ones, the approach proposed in the current work incorporates key-elements for characterizing M-IMUs for human motion analysis, that were not considered in previous works, i.e. the right choice of the frequency and amplitude ranges of the movements to be executed by the robot according to the intended application, and the quantification and management of the magnetic disturbance.

The presented approach, in fact, takes into account a systematic functional frequency and amplitude validation, propaedeutic for the upper limb kinematic analysis, exploiting the high-accuracy and repeatability of an anthropomorphic robot in generating angular trajectories. The amplitude and frequency ranges tested in this work cover the entire spectrum of movement amplitudes and frequencies of the human upper limbs, thus allowing a complete characterization of the sensors. The regression analysis conducted on the *RMSE* with respect to the amplitude ranges can be exploited to estimate the sensors behaviour outside the tested range. Furthermore, the presented approach not only quantifies the magnetic disturbance induced by the robot on the sensors, but also manages and overcomes this problem by exploiting a 3D-printed flange that houses the sensors and keeps them far from the robot motor.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a complete validation protocol for M-IMU characterization is described and validated. The proposed approach is composed of two experimental acquisition phases aiming at characterizing the sensor tracking accuracy at different frequency and amplitude values, typical of human movement. Moreover, this workflow can be exploited to characterize the sensor behaviour for different applications as well as the sensor fusion algorithms implemented into the measurement

Fig. 8. *RMSE* of the trials acquired during the amplitude validation phase for the two sensor systems.

unit. As a preliminary step, the assessment of magnetic disturbance needs to be conducted before performing the frequency and amplitude validation trials. To prove the effectiveness of the method, two different M-IMUs, i.e. the WISE system and Xsens, are tested. In particular, the experimental validation of the proposed method is conducted by taking into account the motion characteristics of the human upper limb movement.

The frequency validation phase evidences that the WISE and Xsens M-IMUs return errors lower than 0.087 rad for the 87.96% and 71.30% of the performed trials and that the error increases with the frequency. The two M-IMUs are capable of accurately tracking all the RoMs spanned in the second validation phase, except for *sIE* and *wPS* movements in which higher angular errors are computed.

The protocol described in this work allows defining an optimal working range in terms of frequency and amplitude of the motion to be tracked.

REFERENCES

- [1] Isabelle Poitras et al. "Validity and reliability of wearable sensors for joint angle estimation: A systematic review". In: *Sensors* 19.7 (2019), p. 1555.
- [2] Francesca Cordella et al. "Patient performance evaluation using Kinect and Monte Carlo-based finger tracking". In: *2012 4th IEEE RAS & EMBS International Conference on Biomedical Robotics and Biomechanics (BioRob)*. IEEE, 2012, pp. 1967–1972.
- [3] Christian Tamantini et al. "The WGD—A Dataset of Assembly Line Working Gestures for Ergonomic Analysis and Work-Related Injuries Prevention". In: *Sensors* 21.22 (2021), p. 7600.
- [4] Diego Álvarez et al. "Upper limb joint angle measurement in occupational health". In: *Computer Methods in Biomechanics and Biomedical Engineering* 19.2 (2016), pp. 159–170.
- [5] Corrin P Walmsley et al. "Measurement of upper limb range of motion using wearable sensors: a systematic review". In: *Sports medicine-open* 4.1 (2018), p. 53.
- [6] James Connolly et al. "IMU sensor-based electronic goniometric glove for clinical finger movement analysis". In: *IEEE Sensors Journal* 18.3 (2017), pp. 1273–1281.
- [7] Olimpio Galasso et al. "The latissimus dorsi tendon functions as an external rotator after arthroscopic-assisted transfer for massive irreparable posterolateral rotator cuff tears". In: *Knee Surgery, Sports Traumatology, Arthroscopy* (2019), pp. 1–10.
- [8] Martina Lapresa et al. "A Smart Solution for Proprioceptive Rehabilitation through M-IMU Sensors". In: *2020 IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for Industry 4.0 & IoT*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 591–595.
- [9] Nicolas Vignais et al. "Innovative system for real-time ergonomic feedback in industrial manufacturing". In: *Applied ergonomics* 44.4 (2013), pp. 566–574.
- [10] Xuzhong Yan et al. "Wearable IMU-based real-time motion warning system for construction workers' musculoskeletal disorders prevention". In: *Automation in Construction* 74 (2017), pp. 2–11.
- [11] Francesco Caputo et al. "Imu-based motion capture wearable system for ergonomic assessment in industrial environment". In: *International Conference on Applied Human Factors and Ergonomics*. Springer, 2018, pp. 215–225.
- [12] Francesco Scotto di Luzio et al. "Visual vs vibrotactile feedback for posture assessment during upper-limb robot-aided rehabilitation". In: *Applied ergonomics* 82 (2020), p. 102950.
- [13] Zhi-Qiang Zhang, Wai-Choong Wong, and Jian-Kang Wu. "Ubiquitous human upper-limb motion estimation using wearable sensors". In: *IEEE Transactions on Information Technology in Biomedicine* 15.4 (2011), pp. 513–521.
- [14] Cyntia Duc et al. "A wearable inertial system to assess the cervical spine mobility: Comparison with an optoelectronic-based motion capture evaluation". In: *Medical engineering & physics* 36.1 (2014), pp. 49–56.
- [15] Philipp Müller et al. "Alignment-free, self-calibrating elbow angles measurement using inertial sensors". In: *IEEE journal of biomedical and health informatics* 21.2 (2016), pp. 312–319.
- [16] G Ligorio et al. "A novel functional calibration method for real-time elbow joint angles estimation with magnetic-inertial sensors". In: *Journal of biomechanics* 54 (2017), pp. 106–110.
- [17] Jaime Hislop et al. "Validation of 3-Space Wireless Inertial Measurement Units Using an Industrial Robot". In: *Sensors* 21.20 (2021), p. 6858.
- [18] Bryan Kirling, Mahmoud El-Gohary, and Young Kwon. "The feasibility of shoulder motion tracking during activities of daily living using inertial measurement units". In: *Gait & posture* 49 (2016), pp. 47–53.
- [19] M. El-Gohary and J. McNames. "Human Joint Angle Estimation with Inertial Sensors and Validation with A Robot Arm". In: *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering* 62.7 (2015), pp. 1759–1767. DOI: 10.1109/TBME.2015.2403368.
- [20] Luca Ricci, Fabrizio Taffoni, and Domenico Formica. "On the orientation error of IMU: investigating static and dynamic accuracy targeting human motion". In: *PLoS One* 11.9 (2016), e0161940.
- [21] Mauro Callejas-Cuervo, Rafael M Gutierrez, and Andres I Hernandez. "Joint amplitude MEMS based measurement platform for low cost and high accessibility telerehabilitation: Elbow case study". In: *Journal of Bodywork and Movement Therapies* 21.3 (2017), pp. 574–581.
- [22] Benjamin Kane Williams et al. "Reliability and validation of an inertial sensor used to measure orientation angle". In: *ISBS-Conference Proceedings Archive*. 2016.
- [23] Kenneth A Mann, Frederick W Wernere, and Andrew K Palmer. "Frequency spectrum analysis of wrist motion for activities of daily living". In: *Journal of Orthopaedic research* 7.2 (1989), pp. 304–306.
- [24] Eugenia Papaleo et al. "Patient-tailored adaptive robotic system for upper-limb rehabilitation". In: *2013 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*. IEEE, 2013, pp. 3860–3865.
- [25] Ya Tian, Hongxing Wei, and Jindong Tan. "An adaptive-gain complementary filter for real-time human motion tracking with MARG sensors in free-living environments". In: *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering* 21.2 (2012), pp. 254–264.
- [26] Donna C Boone and Stanley P Azen. "Normal range of motion of joints in male subjects." In: *JBJS* 61.5 (1979), pp. 756–759.
- [27] C. C. Finlay et al. "International Geomagnetic Reference Field: the eleventh generation". In: *Geophysical Journal International* 183.3 (Dec. 2010), pp. 1216–1230.